

Local timber dominated pre-industrial construction: Insights from archival and dendrochronological data

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ABSTRACT

In pre-modern Europe, timber was notoriously difficult and costly to transport on land, therefore it is usually assumed that ordinary buildings – except for those close to navigable watercourses – were constructed using timber from local sources. We hypothesized that species of timber used in constructions prior to the late 19th century were commonly available in forests within a short distance from the location of the constructions. To test this hypothesis, we compared high-resolution archival information on the tree species composition of forests in Moravia (eastern Czech Republic, ca. 27,000 km²) in the 18th and 19th centuries to a database of 1231 dated timber constructions in the same region and period. Our analysis was based on the mutual distances between the locations of timber constructions and the occurrences of forests with the given tree species. We compared real distances with distances obtained through random simulations. Results showed that in more than half of the cases, the tree species from constructions occurred in the forests of the same township. In the rest of the cases, the modal distance values to the centroid of the nearest township where the same species was present in the forests were usually less than two kilometres and distances larger than five kilometres were generally rare. While our results testify to the availability of timber rather than to the direct source of particular pieces of timber, they strongly suggest that timber was usually sourced locally. We believe our interdisciplinary study demonstrated the usefulness of archival data in the research of timber sourcing. For future studies, we see the combination of our approach with dendroprovenancing and other natural scientific methods as the most promising way to gain deeper knowledge on the sourcing of timber.

1. Introduction

Before modern construction materials, such as concrete and steel, became generally available, most buildings in Europe were made of timber, stone and brick. Of these, timber was the most common in the sense that even stone and brick constructions contained timber in their roof and ceiling structure. Many thousands of houses, churches, barns, fortifications etc. were built each year in Europe using huge amounts of timber (Antoine et al., 2024). Timber itself was not necessarily expensive in all places and periods, but transporting it was notoriously difficult and therefore costly. Virtually the only profitable way to transport

timber over longer distances was floating on water (individually or bundled in rafts). Rivers were often modified to allow for timber floating, for example by straightening their beds or by constructing dams and loading platforms along their courses (e.g. Törnlund and Östlund, 2002; Johann, 2019). In later periods, even specialized timber floating canals were constructed in mountain areas. For example the almost 52 km-long Schwarzenberg canal, the construction of which started in 1789 and lasted for more than three decades, connected timber resources in the Bohemian forest to the Vienna markets (Lange, 2004). On larger navigable rivers and at sea, timber could also be transported on ships. Because of the excellent business opportunity long-distance timber trade

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provided in the Middle Ages and Early Modern Period, its economic history has been well-researched. Much is known for example about the timber trade from Poland, Germany, the Baltic states, Russia or Norway to the Low Countries or England (e.g. Kent, 1955; Hutchison, 2012; Banken, 2024).

Land transport of timber, however, was much more problematic. Pre-modern roads were usually in a poor state of repair and impassable during the rainy season. For example, a report from the end of the 18th century from Landshut in Bavaria noted that even though prices were high, wood was rotting away in just a few hours' distance because conditions were not suitable to transport it on land (Radkau, 2012). Steeper terrain also posed almost insurmountable problems (Johann, 2021). Furthermore, timber is very heavy for its bulk and therefore its transport requires considerable animal power. This meant financial as well as workforce constraints: wherever arable agriculture was practised, it had priority regarding the use of draught animals and the number of such animals in any case could not exceed the carrying capacity of particular regions. As a result, it is usually assumed that ordinary, low status buildings in pre-modern European settlements – except for those close to navigable watercourses – were preferably constructed using timber from local sources within a few dozen kilometres (Bridge, 2012). This situation changed only with the arrival of railway transport, which completely rearranged the former distribution network of many commodities. For the timber trade, this meant not only easier access to supra-regional resources but also the rapid expansion of the so-called “timber frontier” to previously inaccessible regions (Björklund, 2000).

There are several ways to test the validity of the hypothesis that timber in ordinary constructions came from local forests. Perhaps the best known is dendroprovenancing, which traces the geographic origin of individual pieces of timber by comparing their rings to local chronologies (Eckstein and Wrobel, 2007; Bridge, 2012; Gut, 2018). For example, D'Andrea et al. (2024) showed that low-status timber framed houses in Limoges, France in the 15th century were constructed mainly from trees from forests within a 50-kilometre radius around the city. Eissing and Dittmar (2011) demonstrated that timber in a 16th-century village house was cut either in local forests (oak) or transported from a distance of 20 km (fir) and also that the town of Nuremberg used mainly local timber and even introduced legislation to protect these resources. Seim et al. (2015) showed that medieval church roofs in southwestern Sweden were also constructed from local timber. However, as the original focus of dendroprovenancing was long-distance timber transport (Eckstein and Wrobel, 2007), so far most studies have focused on this aspect (cf. Domínguez-Delmás, 2020). Furthermore, as D'Andrea et al. (2024) noted, dendroprovenancing also has its limitations as regards the exact location of source timber especially if environmental conditions are uniform over larger regions. Therefore, novel methods and multivariate approaches for tracing the origins of wood have been tested, such as aDNA (Wagner et al., 2018), the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ strontium isotope ratio (Rich et al., 2015), quantitative wood anatomy (D'Andrea et al., 2022), stable isotopes (Kagawa and Leavitt, 2010) or a combination of these (Akhmetzyanov et al., 2019; Domínguez-Delmás et al., 2020; D'Andrea et al., 2023).

While we acknowledge the usefulness and potential of dendroprovenancing and other studies, in this paper we follow a different, complementary and interdisciplinary approach. We focus on the connection between species of trees used in various constructions and the availability of these species in contemporary forests. We use spatially high-resolution archival information on the tree species composition of forests in a Central European region in the 18th and 19th centuries and compare this information to a large database of dated timbers from constructions in the same region and period. We hypothesize that the species of timber used in constructions prior to the late 19th century were commonly available in forests within a short distance from the location of the constructions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area covers Moravia and Czech Silesia (together c. 27,000 km²) in the eastern half of the Czech Republic in Central Europe (Fig. 1). Although these two territorial units had different origins, in the study period they often formed part of a common administrative framework and therefore for the purposes of this paper we refer to them together as Moravia. The area is made up of 3567 townships, i.e. villages and their surrounding lands including arable fields, forests, meadows and pastures. Townships are historically the lowest tier of local administration, whose territories were formalized in the 18th century resulting in an average size of ca. 7.5 km² (Szabó et al., 2017). Climate in Moravia is mild with mean annual temperatures of 1–10°C and precipitation of 500–1500 mm (Tolasz et al., 2007). The area includes agricultural lowlands in the southern and central parts, highlands in the west and mountains of max. 1491 m a.s.l in the north and east. Approximately one third of the area is covered by forests. The main types currently include thermophilous oak (*Quercus* spp.), oak-hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*), beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and spruce (*Picea abies*) forests. Especially spruce has increased through planting in the past two centuries. Another significant change in tree species composition in the recent past has been the almost complete disappearance of the previously very common silver fir (*Abies alba*).

2.2. Data sources

2.2.1. Archival data

Although much information is available on the tree species composition of Moravian forests from the Middle Ages and Early Modern Period, such data often have coarse spatial resolution and do not cover the entire study area (Szabó et al., 2018). The earliest conscriptions of tree species composition in Moravia that are available in high resolution for each township are the so-called Josephian and Stable cadastres, both compiled for taxation purposes by the Habsburg authorities.

The Josephian cadastre (named after Emperor Joseph II) was drawn up in 1787–1789 as the first cadastre to survey all land regardless of ownership with the same methodology. It included the so-called *Wald-Fassion*, describing the size and position of forests, their management and dominant tree species in each township. Trees were recorded using common names, which usually denote genera in the modern botanical sense (beech, oak, spruce, fir, pine, willow, ash). Nevertheless, several of these genera were represented by a single species (e.g. *Fagus sylvatica*, *Picea abies*, *Abies alba*) in Moravia until forestry plantations of non-native species became common in the late 19th century. Even though tree species composition was a compulsory element of the survey, in many cases the surveyors unfortunately distinguished only two categories: hardwood and softwood. From among the tree species that occur in the dendrochronological database (see below, chapter 2.2.2.), oak belonged to hardwoods, while fir, spruce and pine to softwoods.

The Stable cadastre (so called because it was supposed to last ‘forever’) consisted of three parts: geometric surveying, written surveying and evaluation (Bičák et al., 2015). In Moravia, geometric surveying was carried out between 1824 and 1836, concurrent with written surveying and followed by evaluation (i.e. establishing the monetary value of each parcel for taxation). The written survey and evaluation included surveys of forests as well, recording size, boundaries, dominant tree species and management. Most of the written forest surveys in Moravia are from the 1840s, while the Stable cadastre as such took legal effect only in 1851. As opposed to the Josephian cadastre, the Stable cadastre took decades to complete and therefore establishing any year as its exact date of origin is problematic. For the purposes of this paper, we took 1840 as the cut-off date, as we think this year represents a reasonable compromise between fieldwork and office work during the extremely complex and long-lasting work of preparing this cadastre.

Fig. 1. Map of the study area in Central Europe with dots indicating the locations of timber constructions (a) and examples of dendrochronological (b) and archival (c) data sources.

The availability of these two cadastral surveys offers an excellent opportunity to test our hypothesis on two datasets. As far as we know, the two surveys were independent of each other, therefore congruent results can reinforce our conclusions. For cadastral data, we used the methodology and database described in Szabó et al. (2018). Townships mentioned in the cadastres were identified with modern townships. This introduces certain ambiguities into the system but appears as the only workable solution on the level of 3567 townships, whose exact historical boundaries were only described as text (Josephian cadastre) or have not yet been digitized from the original maps (Stable cadastre) (Szabó et al., 2017). To reduce potential errors connected to changes in the boundaries of townships (cf. Frajer, 2019), we used the centroids rather than outer boundaries of townships in our calculations. Data on tree species composition was extracted for each township from both surveys. Whereas in the Stable cadastre data for tree species was reasonably complete without major gaps or ambiguities, in the Josephian cadastre we had to use for 425 and 811 townships data on hardwood and softwood, respectively, and aggregate these data with townships where data on tree species were available, i.e. oak + hardwood, pine + softwood, spruce + softwood, fir + softwood.

2.2.2. Dendrochronological data

All dendrochronological data were extracted from the Czech dendrochronological database (www.dendrochronologie.cz), which includes almost nine thousand dated historical and archaeological wooden remains from the current territory of the Czech Republic from prehistory to the 20th century. We extracted all dated constructions 50 years before and after each cadastral survey. That is, constructions dated to the period 1740–1840 and 1790–1890 were used in the analyses of the Josephian cadastre and the Stable cadastre, respectively. On the one hand, we assume that forest surveys also reflect the period before the cadastres were published. On the other hand, conifers (mainly spruce and fir) reached the most suitable diameter and height for timber constructions between 70 and 100 years of tree age, as reflected by both contemporary literature (Jondl, 1840) and the mean length of the dated series (approx. 80 years) in our database. We therefore opted for this method of selection to ensure that the dendrochronological data are compatible with the realities of forests as described in the cadastres.

Thanks to the presence of the outermost tree ring (the so-called waney edge), we were able to determine the exact year (or even the season) when the tree used for construction timber was felled (Kolář et al., 2022).

In total, we used 1231 precisely dated historical timber constructions (623 for the Josephian cadastre and 608 for the Stable cadastre). These constructions were mainly residential and farm houses, churches, castles and monasteries. Most of the timber came from either roof constructions or ceiling beams with 65 % and 19 %, respectively. The vast majority (99 %) of the constructions in the study area were made of fir, spruce, pine, and oak (Kolář et al., 2021), therefore we selected for the following analyses only these four species. In our dataset, fir was the most common (682 constructions, 55 %), followed by spruce (329, 27 %), pine (124, 10 %) and oak (96, 8 %). Since historical buildings were not always constructed using only a single tree species, two different species-specific constructions were considered for the analysis if two or more species were identified in one construction.

2.3. Spatial analyses

To test our hypothesis for the individual tree species, we adopted a methodological approach based on the analysis of the mutual distance between constructions using the given tree species and townships where the species was present in local forests, as described below.

First, we tested whether the spatial distribution of the timber constructions in the study area differs from random distribution. A significant deviation from randomness may indicate that the real spatial arrangement of timber constructions is the result of certain processes or phenomena. We used a simple Clark-Evans test for randomness (Clark and Evans, 1954). This test computes R statistics as a ratio between the real (calculated from data) and expected (derived from a theoretical model) mean distance to the nearest neighbour. We tested the null hypothesis on randomness against the alternative hypothesis of a clustered distribution of constructions. Results based on the nearest neighbour distance may be biased due to the fact that timber constructions close to the borders may have the nearest neighbour hypothetically outside the study area. To correct for this 'edge effect', we applied a guard correction (Yamada and Rogerson, 2003). This approach first defines an inner

buffer zone. Constructions in this zone are allowed as neighbours, however, their nearest neighbour distances are not used in R statistics calculation.

In the second step, we used the concept of the nearest neighbour in order to investigate the spatial interaction of the constructions and the forested townships closest to them. For this purpose, we used the cross G-function (Baddeley et al., 2016). More formally, $G_{ij}(r)$ quantifies the probability distribution of timber construction (i) nearest to the centroid of forested townships (j) within a given distance (r). Whereas theoretical G^{Pois} represents distribution of the nearest neighbour distances under complete spatial randomness (CSR), G^{bord} is a G-function from observed data and applying the same edge effect correction as explained above.

We then combined the two spatial databases in the form of maps, in which we distinguished two types of constructions based on whether the tree species in them occurred in the forests of the same township or not. For each construction whose tree species was not available in the forests in the same township, we calculated the distance to the nearest township with the given tree species. The distance was calculated from the position of the construction to the nearest centroid of a township with the given tree species.

We characterized the distribution of the closest distances of constructions to forested townships with their histograms. Considering the asymmetric right skewed shape of the histograms, we used the modal, i. e. the most frequent distance as the typical distance between constructions and forested townships. Subsequently, we randomly generated the position of the same number of constructions in the entire study area. For 999 simulations, we calculated the modal value of the closest distances of the constructions to forested townships and compiled a probability density function (pdf) from all simulated modal values. Using the pdf function, we calculated the probability of occurrence of the modal distance of constructions to forested townships calculated from observed data. The modal values represented only about 30 % of the closest observed distances of constructions from forested townships for all the tree species studied. Therefore, we repeated the same procedure for a stricter criterion, namely the distance of the third quartile, that is, the distance greater than 75 % of all observed distances. All computations were conducted in the spatstat R package (Baddeley and Turner, 2005).

3. Results

The Clark-Evans test demonstrated in all cases that the distribution of the locations of constructions differed significantly from random distribution and showed clustering (Table 1). The number of constructions located directly within townships with the occurrence of the given timber species and outside such townships was relatively similar in most of the eight studied cases (four tree species times two cadastral surveys). The highest and lowest proportions of constructions within townships with the given timber species were found for spruce and oak, respectively. The overall distribution of the distances of constructions from the nearest township with the occurrence of the given tree species was strongly asymmetric and positively skewed (see Table 1 and also the first columns of Figs. 6 and 7). This means a significant predominance of short distances. For instance, the most common distances (mode) varied from 606 to 1365 m and even the third quartile (Q75) distances mostly did not exceed 6000 m (highest value: 6059 m for fir in the Stable cadastre). However, in individual cases, the maximum distance of constructions from forest occurrence exceeded even 40 kilometres (such as for fir and spruce in the Stable cadastre). In effect, this means that the tree species in constructions in our dendrochronological database were usually available in a township within a few kilometres from the location of the construction. There were no major differences between the Josephian and Stable cadastres concerning these values.

The cross-G functions reinforced the notion that the locations of constructions and the centroids of townships where the given tree species occurred were typically close to each other (Figs. 2 and 3). Each plot contains two functions. G_{bord} above G_{Pois} represents positive

association (attraction), which means that many constructions and the nearest centroids of relevant townships were close to each other compared to CSR. Conversely, G_{bord} below G_{Pois} expresses negative association (repulsion), in which constructions very rarely occur close to the centroids of forested township compared to CSR. In most cases in both cadastral surveys, coniferous species in constructions and forests showed positive association until ca. 1500–2500 m and negative association above that value. In other words, at short distances their common distribution was more clustered than it would have been under a random pattern. Oak, however, showed positive association through almost the entire range of distance values in both surveys. In addition, the cut-off value between attraction and repulsion showed somewhat higher values for the Stable cadastre than for the Josephian cadastre. Overall, the analyses confirmed the hypothesis that the specific species of timber used in constructions in the study period were commonly available in forests within a short distance from the location of the constructions.

Figs. 4 and 5 summarise the spatial distribution of timber constructions and townships with the occurrence of the four tree species. Fir and spruce grew in higher-lying regions in the west, north and east, whereas oak was commonly found in the southern and central lowland areas. Pine was absent in the highest mountains but its area included some of the lowlands. The individual maps demonstrate that the constructions located furthest from relevant forested townships - at least for spruce, fir and pine - were mainly located in the southern part of Moravia, in the lowlands near the Austrian border.

Figs. 6 and 7 summarise the main results of two simulations whose aim was to quantify the extent to which the observed distances of constructions from the nearest relevant forested townships differed from the distances that would have been observed in the case of a purely random distribution of constructions. We compared two characteristics of the distance of real constructions from forests (mode and Q75) with the same characteristics obtained from 999 random simulations. The simulations demonstrated that the probability of the occurrence of the modal value of real data was very low in all cases. It was mostly less than 1 % and only slightly higher (4 %) for pine and oak in the Josephian cadastre. Similarly small probabilities were obtained in the case of the Q75 simulations for all studied tree species in the Stable cadastre and for spruce and oak in the Josephian cadastre. However, for pine and especially for fir in the Josephian cadastral survey, the probabilities of real distances in the distribution of simulated Q75 values were quite high. In other words, these two cases indicate that the occurrence of constructions further from forested townships was not exceptional. In sum, except for two cases out of sixteen, the simulations overwhelmingly demonstrated that timber species used in constructions were statistically significantly closer to forests where such species grew than they would have been under random distribution.

4. Discussion

4.1. Local sources of construction timber

Our analyses showed that the tree species used in constructions in the 18th and 19th centuries in Moravia were in the vast majority of cases available in local forests and that specific species of timber were rarely used far away from local sources. In more than half of the cases, the tree species from constructions occurred in the forests of the same township. In the rest of the cases, the modal distance values to the centroid of the nearest township where the same species was present in the forests were usually less than two kilometres and distances larger than five kilometres were generally rare. It is nonetheless important to keep in mind that our analyses concerned the availability of tree species rather than the precise geographical origin of particular pieces of construction timber. The question then arises whether or not socioeconomic conditions were favourable for the local procurement of timber for building purposes in the 18th and 19th centuries in Moravia. Generally speaking,

Table 1

Number of timber constructions and their characteristic distances to the centroids of the nearest township with the occurrence of the given tree species for individual tree species according to the Josephian and Stable cadastres.

tree species	source	constructions in township with species		constructions in township without species		distance from centroid of nearest township with species (m)						Clark-Evans test, Guard correction	
		n	%	n	%	min.	1st quarter	median	mean	mode	3d quarter	max.	R
fir	Josephian cadastre	190	54 %	161	46 %	72	666	1427	2320	763	3607	16567	0.61694*
	Stable cadastre	118	36 %	213	64 %	72	1023	2880	5488	1365	6059	44500	0.61209*
spruce	Josephian cadastre	108	73 %	39	27 %	120	545	892	1686	606	1824	16567	0.60953*
	Stable cadastre	113	62 %	69	38 %	19	563	982	4041	661	2520	44500	0.56673*
pine	Josephian cadastre	28	43 %	37	57 %	222	824	2098	2951	1073	4050	16567	0.60798*
	Stable cadastre	34	58 %	25	42 %	126	633	1600	3202	665	2814	20636	0.73171*
oak	Josephian cadastre	21	35 %	39	65 %	439	936	2168	2447	1105	3312	8448	0.79275*
	Stable cadastre	18	50 %	18	50 %	367	846	2020	2321	930	3097	8069	0.74831*

* all R values are significant at < 0.001

Fig. 2. The expected ($G_{TC,JC}^{pois}$) and observed ($G_{TC,JC}^{bord}$) cross-G functions representing the cumulative distribution of the nearest-neighbour distances between timber constructions and the centroids of the nearest townships where the given tree species occurred based on the Josephian cadastre. $G_{TC,JC}^{pois}$ represents the distribution of the nearest neighbour distances under complete spatial randomness. $G_{TC,JC}^{bord}$ assumes edge correction due to no information about the data outside the study area (see text for explanation).

there were two ways for non-noble subjects to acquire construction timber in this period. It was either taken from local forests to which members of the community had free access or, and this was much more common, it had to be bought from demesne forests, which represented the vast majority of all forests in Moravia (Szabó, 2021). In the first case,

the source of timber naturally had to be nearby. The same was probably true for the second case as well, because end users usually cut the timber themselves and had to pay for transportation.

The above considerations together with the combined evidence of 1231 timber constructions and detailed archival sources on coeval forest

Fig. 3. The expected (G_{pois}) and observed (G_{bord}) cross-G functions representing the cumulative distribution of the nearest-neighbour distances between timber constructions and the centroids of the nearest townships where the given tree species occurred based on the Stable cadastre.

tree species composition suggest that people used local sources of construction timber and tried to avoid transporting timber over longer distances as much as possible. As succinctly put by the author of the forest management instructions attached to the 1754 Bohemian forest law: „one can easily perceive the advantages of tree cultivation, as many reasonable farmers have experienced, especially when one has timber close-by and does not have to procure it from far away for heavy costs and transport wages.”¹

Land transport of timber to distant places was a notable exception even for the wealthy. In the early 1570 s, for example, Emperor Maximilian II ordered 600 larch (*Larix decidua*) timbers to be brought to Prague castle from Bruntál, ca. 220 km towards the east as the crow flies (Nožička, 1962b). Even if the trees could be transferred onto the Labe river around Pardubice, most of the journey had to be taken on land, which may explain why the Emperor had to repeatedly urge the local authorities and why it took more than a year for the timbers to eventually arrive in Prague. Such extraordinary measures were necessary because larch had some unique qualities but grew only in one small region of the Czech lands (Dudová and Szabó, 2022). Paying for transport, however, could be reduced or avoided in certain cases. For example, peasants in certain villages were obliged to transport timber for the overlord as part of their corvée labour (Chadt, 1913). These factors may have resulted in differences in the average distances between timber species and corresponding forests in the case of rural versus ecclesiastical/noble constructions (cf. Kolár et al., 2022). However, our post-hoc analyses revealed no such differences, and therefore we did not present these results in our investigations.

Forestry writers of the period were acutely aware of the difficulties involved in the land transport of timber. The second edition of Heinrich Cotta's seminal *Grundriß der Forstwissenschaft* (Fundamentals of forest science) contained a description of various ways of land and water transport, emphasizing that “transport by water is generally the more economical method and will therefore always be preferred where both methods are equally applicable” (Cotta, 1836). In a similar manner, the most authoritative book on timber transport, entitled *Handbuch für Holztransport- und Floßwesen* (Handbook of wood transport and rafting) devoted less than 200 pages to land transport as opposed to 600 pages describing water transport (Jägerschmid, 1827–1828). The greatest contemporary encyclopaedia of the German speaking world (initiated by Johann Georg Krünitz) discussed the financial aspects of the land transport of timber in more detail. According to this work, transporting timber to a distance of 2 miles (approximately 15 km, using the ‘German’ mile as defined in the encyclopaedia itself) cost 2–4 thaler, whereas the cost of timber per piece (depending on size and quality) was 6–12 thaler (Krünitz, 1781). To interpret these numbers, the concept of “theoretical supply radius” introduced by Galloway et al. (1996) can be used. This uses the formula $R = (P - C) / T$, where R is the radius in kilometres, P is the price, C is the production cost and T is the cost of transport per kilometre. In other words, the number of kilometres a piece of timber is worth transporting equals the number of times its price (minus production costs) was higher than transportation costs per kilometre. Computing with the average values of 3 thaler per 2 miles and 9 thaler per timber, we arrive at a radius of 6 miles, or ca. 45 km, which should be somewhat reduced because of the lack of information on production costs. The same encyclopaedia also added that timber could be transported at best 3–3.5 miles a day, which means that economically viable transport could last a maximum of 2 days. German forester

¹ Národní archiv Praha, PT, inventární číslo 1498–5.4.1754.

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of fir, spruce, pine and oak trees in Moravian forests based on data in the Josephian cadastre (shaded areas). In 811 townships only 'softwood' and in 425 townships only 'hardwood' was distinguished, the pertinent category is therefore combined with the distribution of the given tree species. Dots indicate the locations of constructions distinguishing whether the given tree species was (red) or was not (blue) available in the forests of the same township. The size of the blue dot shows the distance to the centroid of the nearest township where the given tree species was available.

Hieronimus Hauck in 1866 provided much less optimistic numbers, when he claimed that timber could be profitably transported on land at most 10 hours (Schenk, 1996). Although these numbers do not directly apply to our study region, they provide contemporary context, which indicates that the typical distance between timber species in constructions and forests in Moravia was rather small. Unfortunately, there are no similar data available in the literature for Moravia. As an example of just how costly land transport could be, we quote the 1869–1871 account books of the Pozořice estate (southern Moravia), where the transport of a sack of charcoal on carts from the production places in the forests to the nearby ironworks represented almost the same amount as the wages paid to charcoal burners to produce the same one sack of charcoal and approximately ten times more than the hard work of preparing one charcoal burning platform in the local hilly terrain.² It should be added that the availability of construction timber, its price and the economics of transport could in some cases be also greatly influenced by the effects of windstorms (Brázdil et al., 2018) or bark beetle outbreaks (Brázdil et al., 2022). Overall, even if one allows for the possibility that timber was not always procured from the nearest available source, our results still fall well within the range that implies a lack of long-distance land transport of timber.

A further question is how far one can generalize our results in a European context. Bridge's (2012) thesis on local timber sources, quoted in the Introduction, is applicable only in regions, such as ours, which had a sufficiently high forest cover. However, in many areas of especially

North-Western Europe, there were few forests left by the end of the Middle Ages. Construction timber therefore often had to be brought from longer distances, or re-used, even modifying architectural styles to reflect the lack of resources (e.g. Dixon, 2001, Haneca et al., 2020). Timber shortages, while probably localized, were typical for many parts of Europe in the 18th and 19th centuries (Warde, 2006). In these regions, acquiring building timber formed part of a more complicated network of socioeconomic and natural factors than in our study area.

4.2. Timber rafting

In the Czech Lands, like elsewhere in Europe (Hollister-Short, 1994), timber was transported over longer distances with the help of navigable waterways with documents going back to the Middle Ages for example in the case timber rafting to Prague (Holec, 1971; Svoboda, 2018). Large amounts of trees were floated especially from mountainous areas towards the central lowlands or, if gravity allowed, also towards foreign markets (Nožička, 1962a). In our case, the question arises whether timber found in constructions at larger distances from forests could be floated on rivers. It is, however, rather difficult to find an answer to this question at present. First, there has been little research on the topic in Moravia as opposed to Bohemia. Second, such research as exists has focused on larger rivers, and the suitability of smaller watercourses, which make up the vast majority of the water network of Moravia, for floating in the study period is not known. To evaluate possible patterns, we examined the position of timber constructions in our database in relation to the nearest watercourse including simulations similar to those described in chapter 2.3. Because of the dense network of small

² Moravský zemský archiv F 82 karton 1100.

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of fir, spruce, pine and oak trees in Moravian forests based on data in the Stable cadastre (shaded areas). For the interpretation of red and blue dots, see legend to Fig. 4.

ivers, the results showed very low values. However, such numbers have probably little to do with coeval realities. A centrally commissioned overview of all Moravian rivers in 1826 claimed that the only rivers used for timber floating were the Morava and the Bečva (Jerábek, 1961). Even if this claim was probably exaggerated, it still indicates that rafting may not have been very common. Nonetheless, some patterns visible in our maps suggest that the distribution of fir and spruce in constructions in the 19th century might be connected to the courses of major rivers flowing through Brno (Fig. 5).

4.3. Limitations of the sources and methods

Although the results in most cases confirm our working hypothesis that the species of timber used in constructions were available in local forests, they may be affected by several uncertainties. First, cadastral surveys typically recorded only dominant tree species. The absence of locally rare species in the archival sources means that in some cases the distance between constructions and nearest relevant forested townships could be artificially enlarged. However, as more precise archival data would only have reduced these distances, this presents no significant problem as regards the interpretation of the results. A similar issue is that of the precision of archival data: the resolution of cadastral information is the township rather than individual forests. In other words, the centroids we used in our calculations do not exactly match the locations of forests where the pertinent tree species occurred. However, as mentioned above, the average size of townships is 7.5 km², which translates to a radius of ca. 1.5 km. In other words, even if in the majority of cases the actual forests where the given tree species occurred had been in the most distant part of the township, our results would not be radically altered. A third problem is the possible ‘edge effect’ of constructions near the southern border of Moravia, where some of the

timber may have come from nearby forests in Austria, especially considering the transboundary possessions of significant noble families (Merki and Löffler, 2013). However, the two sides of the boundary are biogeographically rather similar, therefore the coniferous tree species recorded in our dendrochronological data are unlikely to have been more common in forests on the Austrian side.

It is also worth considering the differences between the Josephian and Stable cadastres. Information on tree species distribution in the former is much less precise, because, in lack of other information, we had to use the categories ‘hardwood’ and ‘softwood’ for many townships. This should blur the distinction between fir, spruce and pine, all of which are softwoods. Furthermore, many common broadleaved trees, for example, birch, poplar or lime, also belong among softwoods. This means that in particular cases the distance between the construction and the nearest township with the same tree species could be larger than our results suggest. Nonetheless, notable differences occurred only in Q75 values, where simulations for the Josephian cadastre showed non-significant values for fir and pine. In the case of fir, we believe this testifies to the almost universal presence of the species (including ‘softwood’ occurrences) combined with its widespread distribution in constructions, which showed the highest number of all tree species in all periods and surveys. As for pine, we probably witness a similar situation but with overall lower numbers. In this case, a further confounding factor could be the general tendency for pine constructions to occur at relatively lower elevations, where pine formed forests together with a number of broadleaved softwood tree species.

5. Conclusions

Our results confirmed the hypothesis that tree species used in constructions in Moravia in the 18th and 19th centuries were generally

Fig. 6. Empirical (histogram) and theoretical (probability density function) distribution of the closest distances between real (left) and simulated (middle and right) locations of timber constructions and the occurrence of individual tree species based on the Josephian cadastre. Vertical lines indicate modal (blue) and Q75 (red) distances calculated from the real positions of the constructions. Note the different scales of the x and y axes.

available in local forests. While this demonstrates a pattern of probable supply areas, our data do not directly reveal that timber was in fact sourced locally. Nonetheless, in light of all other factors discussed above, this seems to have been the most likely scenario. This paper then adds to a growing body of literature discussing networks of timber supply in pre-modern Europe. As opposed to the more common dendroprovenancing studies, the novelty in our approach was the comparison of detailed and high-resolution archival data (i.e. contemporary information on forests) with a dendrochronological database. We believe our interdisciplinary study demonstrated the usefulness of archival data in the research of timber sourcing. For future studies, we see the combination of our

approach with dendroprovenancing and other natural scientific methods as the most promising way to gain deeper knowledge on the sourcing of timber in pre-modern Europe.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Szabó Péter: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Rybníček Michal:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Kyncl Josef:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Dobrovolný Petr:** Writing – review & editing,

Fig. 7. Empirical (histogram) and theoretical (probability density function) distribution of the closest distances between real (left) and simulated (middle and right) locations of timber constructions and the occurrence of individual tree species based on the Stable cadastre. Vertical lines indicate modal (blue) and Q75 (red) distances calculated from the real position of the constructions. Note the different scales of the x and y axes.

Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kolár Tomáš:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kyncl Tomáš:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data on the locations of timber constructions for the individual tree species are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14801669>.

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